

PREPARING FUTURE DEFECTOLOGISTS FOR ORGANIZING BINARY LESSONS IN AN INCLUSIVE EDUCATION ENVIRONMENT BASED ON THE PRINCIPLES OF AN EDUCATIONAL CLUSTER

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Annotation

This article discusses the preparation of future defectologists for the organization of binary lessons in an inclusive education environment based on the principles of an educational cluster.

Keywords

Defectologist, inclination education, principle, cerebral palsy.

Today, the work of a defectologist includes a lot of corrective work. Including children with disabilities. As you know, in recent years, special pedagogy has been developing, including defectology. They try to raise children with disabilities with healthy children. And it gives good results. With the help of this, inclusive education is being introduced. If we look at history, then we will remember that there was an inclusive break before, but this was not said much. Children with cerebral deficiencies, children with poor hearing, children with low vision, some of them studied with healthy peers.

In the modern world, the number of children with disabilities who experience difficulties in mastering the educational program is increasing. They require the creation of special conditions for training and education, and there is a need for comprehensive support for such children in educational institutions. In other words, there is a need for a barrier-free educational environment that would allow children with disabilities to fully realize their educational needs. In this regard, there is a need to create an inclusive educational space for children with disabilities.

In modern psychological and pedagogical science and practice, the concept of "educational environment" is widely used when discussing the conditions of education and upbringing. Numerous works of domestic and foreign scientists (J. Gibson, V. A. Yasvin, S. V. Tarasov, etc.) are devoted to the study of the problems of the educational environment.

The educational environment is considered as a subsystem of the historically established socio-cultural environment and at the same time as specially organized pedagogical conditions in which the development of the child's personality is carried out. In this sense, the educational environment is interesting for its functional purpose, in terms of the quality of the educational opportunities it provides for the effective self-development of its subjects. In the context of considering the problems of inclusive education, the concept of the environment is of particular relevance. This is due to the fact that the inclusion of a child with special educational needs imposes new requirements on its organization. The change concerns technological, organizational, methodological, moral, psychological and other parameters.

An inclusive educational environment is a type of educational environment that provides all subjects of the educational process with opportunities for effective self-development. It involves solving the problem of educating children with disabilities by adapting the educational space to the needs of each child, including reforming the educational process, methodological flexibility and variability, a favorable psychological climate, redevelopment of classrooms so that they meet the needs of all children without exception and provide, if possible, full participation of children in the educational process.

The organization of an inclusive educational environment, in our opinion, is based on the following corrective principles.

First. Early inclusion in an inclusive environment. This provides the possibility of habilitation, that is, the initial formation of abilities for social interaction;

Second. Correctional assistance, a child with developmental disorders has compensatory capabilities, it is important to “turn them on”, rely on them in building the educational process. The child, as a rule, quickly adapts to the social environment, however, he requires the organization of a supportive space and special support (which also acts as conditions that take into account his special needs).

Third. Individual orientation of education. A child with disabilities can master a common educational program for all, which is an important condition for his inclusion in the life of the children's team. If necessary, an individual educational route is developed depending on the characteristics, depth of the defect and the capabilities of the child. The route should be flexible, focus on the zone of proximal development, provide for the formation of speech skills, the main types of cognitive activity according to age, and the development of social skills.

Fourth. Team way of working. Specialists, teachers, parents need to work in close relationship (on a team basis), which involves the joint construction of goals and objectives of activities in relation to each child, a joint discussion of the characteristics of the child, his capabilities, the process of his movement in the development and development of socio-pedagogical space.

Fifth. The activity of parents, their responsibility for the results of the development of the child. Parents are full members of the team, so they should be given the opportunity to take an active part in the discussion of the pedagogical process, its dynamics and correction.

Sixth. The priority of socialization as a process and result of inclusion. The main target component in the work is the formation of the child's social skills, mastering the experience of social relations. The child must learn to take an active part in all types of children's activities, not be afraid to express themselves, express their opinions, find friends; developing interpersonal relationships, teach other children to accept themselves as they are. And this, in turn, is possible with a sufficient level of personal and cognitive development of the child.

Seventh. The development of positive interpersonal relationships is not a spontaneous process, it is also the subject of special work of teachers.

Eighth. One of the backbone characteristics of an effective educational environment is its safety (physical and psychological). A psychologically safe environment can be considered an environment in which the majority of participants have a positive attitude towards it; high indicators of the index of satisfaction with interaction and protection from psychological violence (Baeva I.A., Laktionova E.B.).

Based on these principles, an inclusive educational environment is organized in our

educational institution. In order for the environment to comply with the principles, it was necessary to think over the structure of its organization. Having studied the works of E.A. Klimov, V.A. Yasvina, Tarasova S.V., in which the components of the educational environment of the institution are proposed, we singled out the structure of the inclusive educational environment as a space for the socialization of children with different abilities and characteristics, including spatial-objective, content-methodical and communicative-organizational components.

We know that in practice there are various organizational work with children with disabilities. Defectologists for the organization of binary lessons work with a program that includes inclusive education. And this makes it possible to give a good result of inclusive education.

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